

Learning and motivational impact of a social-purpose educational project in engineering students

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ABSTRACT

Active learning methods such as Project-Based Learning (PBL) and Challenge-Based Learning (CBL) are becoming increasingly prevalent in engineering education, however the literature reports few projects with social purpose. This research examines the evolution of a socially committed educational project named OSOR (Open-source and SOcial Responsibility) over four years, focusing on its impact on the learning process, student satisfaction, and perceived difficulty within the context of a Manufacturing Technology course in the Industrial Engineering curriculum. The OSOR raises a relevant social challenge that seeks to locally (and globally) mitigate the lack of assistive products for people who are in a situation of dependency due to accidents or illnesses. We compared the learning outcomes and perceptions of 108 students using both tests and tailored surveys, along with the retrospective evaluation of 64 products resulting from the project. Transitioning from PBL, where students proposed hypothetical cases, to CBL involving real patient cases, boosted student motivation, and learning effectiveness, despite increasing the perceived difficulty.

KEYWORDS

Project-based learning (PBL), Challenge-based learning (CBL), Service learning (SL), Knowledge gain, Motivation for learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Engineering programs often struggle to motivate students due to traditional lectures that overlook diverse learning styles and lack practical application¹. In response, the curricula of European universities are shifting toward practical, learner-centred approaches, broadening the scope of engineering education². Active learning (AL) methods like project- and challenge-based learning are increasingly used to enhance engagement in education³. Global challenges such as climate change, renewable energy, responsible consumption, or migration involve technical, environmental, socio-political, and economical dimensions, as outlined in the United Nations' 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)⁴. Engineers can play a vital role in advancing sustainability through innovation, creating social benefits⁵⁻⁸. Therefore, engineering students must recognize their societal role and be ready for these challenges.

Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET) in USA recommends that engineering students learn to produce solutions in public health, safety, and socio-environmental factors⁹, while the European Network for Accreditation of Engineering Education (ENAAE) emphasizes that they gain interpretation of complex data to inform judgments that include reflection on relevant social and ethical issues¹⁰. SEFI, the European Society for Engineering Education, supports their visions through events focused on social responsibility and sustainability¹¹. These organizations emphasize universities to develop students' technical and interpersonal abilities, as well as their social and global awareness. Despite numerous studies on engineering education¹²⁻¹⁴, research on early methods to enhance students' global awareness and their impact on motivation and learning remains limited^{7,15}.

In this article, the open-source and social responsibility (OSOR) educational strategy addresses a global need identified by the World Health Organization (WHO): assistive products for 2.5 billion people¹⁶. The OSOR engages students in designing and producing aids for individuals who are dependent due to accidents or illness, aligning with key UN Sustainable Development Goals, including Goal 3 ("Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages"), Goal 4 ("Quality Education"), and Goal 10 ("Reduce inequality within and among countries"). Initially, the OSOR project allowed students to propose their own hypothetical cases. Over time, the project evolved to include real cases provided by patients from local institutions. This study examines

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3 the evolution of the OSOR project over four academic years, analysing the implications of these changes on
4 students' learning outcomes and their perceptions of the methodology and the course.
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6 The research questions guiding this study are: (1) How did the OSOR project evolve over the four academic
7 years, (2) What were the implications of altering the responsibility for proposing the cases, and (3) How did
8 the educational framework contribute to enhancing students' learning. We explored this question using a
9 mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data analysis techniques, including
10 academic results, tests, and ad hoc surveys. We expect that insights from this study might improve socially
11 oriented educational projects, fostering well-rounded engineering graduates with the essential socio-technical
12 skills for modern engineers.
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15 **2. CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND**

16 **2.1 Project-based Learning (PBL)**

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19 PBL is an AL strategy based on constructivist and socio-constructivist theories, where students collaborate in
20 teams guided by instructors to face complex real-world problems. It is highly effective in engineering
21 education to promote personal and interpersonal skills such as teamwork, communication, problem-solving,
22 and self-directed learning^{17,18}. In PBL, students build their knowledge through their experiences and
23 interactions¹⁹. Engineering students often report the greatest improvement in teamwork and communication,
24 but lack empathy and cultural perspectives¹⁸.⁷ suggested that socially responsible projects, though scarce in
25 engineering programs, could address these gaps. By integrating PBL in a third-year course,²⁰ demonstrated
26 that engineering students could create products to benefit people in developing countries, providing socio-
27 cultural and sustainable solutions, without compromising their technical appropriateness.
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30 **2.2 Service Learning (SL)**

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33 SL is another AL approach supported in experiential education that emphasizes delivering services to local
34 communities^{15,21}. SL must be approached as a credit-bearing educational experience integrated into the course
35 curriculum, and in which students participate in structured community service activities. Reflective practices
36 in SL strengthen students' comprehension of the course contents, expand disciplinary perspectives, and foster
37 personal growth and civic responsibility²². While effective in promoting engineering students' social
38 awareness, SL is only present in 2% of engineering programs, contrasting with a 30% integration rate in health
39 sciences¹⁵.
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42 **2.3 Challenge-based Learning (CBL)**

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45 CBL offers benefits similar to PBL, but differs by focusing on complex real-world problems that demand
46 innovative, multidisciplinary, and sustainable solutions^{3,23}. It typically addresses environmental, social, or
47 ethical issues^{24,25} and engages students with stakeholders from business, academia, or social sectors who
48 support project teams throughout²⁶. CBL is particularly useful in engineering programs⁵, but it is rarely
49 oriented to social purposes²³. It can effectively develop students' skills such as industry networking, technical
50 abilities, oral communication, teamwork, problem-solving skills, or innovative thinking²⁷.
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53 The PBL, SL and CBL strategies share a similar approach focused on gaining in-depth subject knowledge,
54 developing soft skills, and acquiring a global perspective on the career studied. In social projects, they also
55 enhance students' social awareness and civic responsibility.
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57 **3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK**

58 **3.1 Pedagogical model**

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60 The pedagogical model illustrating the OSOR experience (Fig. 1) is primarily based on Biggs' 3P model of
learning and teaching for higher education²⁸. This model suggests that learning results from a complex and

dynamic process shaped by factors interacting at three distinct stages: (a) *Presage*, before learning occurs; (b) *Process*, during the learning activities; and (c) *Product*, as the outcome of learning.

In the *Presage* phase, the main factors are the teaching context and, more important, the students themselves, whose perceptions of this learning context greatly affect their academic performance²⁹. Analysing these factors alongside the activities occurring during the *Process* stage helps clarify the *Product* of the teaching-learning process. Previous studies^{30–32} based on the same model show that organizational elements such as learning objectives, methodological strategies, assessment, and social support positively influence students' views of the task's usefulness, ease, and their own ability. These positive perceptions can enhance motivation and commitment, leading to more participative students. They can achieve not only better academic performance but also be more resilience, especially in facing their challenges, which strengthens their satisfaction with the learning experience.

Fig. 1. The OSOR pedagogical model, built upon Biggs' 3P framework of learning and teaching

At the start of the semester, the key features of the OSOR are clearly outlined for students: learning objectives, social goals, stakeholders, stages, schedule, evaluation plan, and available resources. This helps students guide their focus, create a structured, easy-to-follow learning environment, and understand the value of the OSOR. Students are also informed they will receive immediate feedback about their performance at each stage to improve their work quality and learning strategies³³. The social impact of OSOR resonates positively with the students, as the products delivered could be useful and enhance lives for those in need, garnering support from family and friends who recognize its value. This social dimension of OSOR is understandable by students' social references, such as family and friends, who might express their support towards achieving the project objectives.

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3 Students face the challenge of developing a product for individuals with physical limitations and should be
4 familiar with the circumstances of people in a dependency situation. Familiarity with the overall structure of
5 the OSOR project can boost students' confidence in achieving success³⁴. Additional measures, such as setting
6 clear milestones and ensuring immediate feedback from instructors, stakeholders, or patients, can further
7 enhance students' confidence to carry out the OSOR project. Summarizing, we aim to create a supportive
8 learning environment that benefits both their professional growth and personal well-being.
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10 11 **3.2 THE OSOR PROJECT**

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13 The OSOR project, designed for an engineering school context in industrial manufacturing technologies,
14 addresses real-world needs by integrating these technologies to build essential skills highlighted in engineering
15 curricula. The project enhances learning through socially meaningful tasks, as students create affordable and
16 sustainable assistive products for individuals in dependency situation, according to the definition of this kind
17 of products formulated by WHO³⁵. Since the 2018-19 academic year, the OSOR has been integrated into the
18 Manufacturing Technology (MT) course, a second-year compulsory subject for all industrial engineering
19 degrees at the university³⁶.
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23 Students work in self-selected teams, typically of three, with a flexible allocated budget, according to the
24 project complexity. They leverage open-source machines available at the university, and benefit from the
25 sharing knowledge about this technology. Their final designs and fabrication instructions are shared online,
26 making OSOR products accessible to everyone.
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29 Although OSOR addresses global issues, incorporating local institutions promotes direct interaction between
30 student teams and patients (or organizations), making it fundamentally a local project. According to several
31 authors²⁷, this feature is crucial because global problems must keep a local focus and applicability. This can
32 be achieved effectively when students work closely with local entities, enhancing the relevance and impact of
33 their projects.
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35 **3.2.1 Main stages of the OSOR project**

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37 Fig. 2 illustrates the four main stages of the OSOR project (*creativity, preliminary project, progress report,*
38 *and final presentation*) along with their timing. The first three stages include brief 5-minute oral presentations
39 that allow students to share key updates with instructors and classmates. This rapid presentation format helps
40 instructors monitor team progress and provide immediate feedback.
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44 In the first week, cases are briefly introduced, and students ask questions and deliberate before selecting a case
45 to work on for the semester. By the next *creativity* stage (second week), teams propose at least three potential
46 solutions, and immediately receive instructor feedback on the feasibility of their proposals. Students then must
47 choose one solution to pursue the rest of the semester. In the fourth week, the teams draft a *preliminary project*
48 outlining requirements in terms of materials and machines, and then assign tasks, and establish the timeline.
49 The rest of the semester teams polish their designs, produce prototypes, and present short *progress reports*
50 every two to three weeks to share updates with their classmates. Two peer evaluations (mid-semester and end-
51 of-semester) are established to facilitate that students self-regulate and manage their learning process³⁷. These
52 data are not included in this article. The final stage is a public *presentation*, with invitations extended to **the**
53 **university community**, local experts, patients, and media³⁸. At the exhibition's conclusion, attendees can vote
54 to select the best product, with winners earning bonus points toward their final grade.
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Fig. 2. Key stages of the OSOR project and their time distribution in weeks

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Context and sample description

The OSOR project was conducted at a public university in the northern region of Spain, with an enrolment of approximately 5.000 students. The study specifically took place at the Higher Technical School of Industrial Engineering (ETSII, in Spanish), which offers three bachelor's degrees in Industrial Engineering: Mechanical, Electrical, and Electronics Engineering. The project has been in progress since the academic year 2018-19 and has involved the subject of MT. This is a second-year mandatory course taught jointly for all ETSII degrees that covers both traditional and advanced manufacturing technologies including machining, casting, welding, metal forming, additive manufacturing, among others. The course consists of 60 hours of in-person classes and 90 hours of self-directed student work over a 15-week semester. **The OSOR weighted 20% of the subject's final score.**

One of the challenges inherent in these teaching strategies is the risk that, by emphasizing the synthesis of knowledge from several subject areas to solve complex problems, the learning process becomes fragmented. This is not our case, as many other activities are carried out alongside the OSOR project in the MT subject, such as lectures, case studies, problem-based learning sessions, online forum discussions, oral presentations, practical sessions and written exams. These activities are specifically designed to reinforce and consolidate key ideas from each area, ensuring that the integrative synthesis is built on a solid foundation. In addition, the use of formative and ongoing assessments helps to identify and address any gaps in understanding, so that students not only connect ideas across subject areas, but also achieve a deep mastery of core concepts.

This study examines the OSOR project over four consecutive academic years (2018-19 to 2021-22) using data from 108 students (84 male, 24 female) out of 204 enrolled in the MT subject (Table 1). A total of 64 products generated from 2018-19, 2020-21, and 2021-22 were evaluated in this study. Data from 2019-20 was excluded due to the low survey participation (12%) during the COVID-19 pandemic. A common behaviour observed by several authors³⁹ that makes the data unrepresentative. Also, most of the practical activities, prototyping, and teamwork were disrupted in 2019-20, which resulted in a significantly low number of products delivered (9%).

The participating students in the academic years included in the OSOR were organized into teams, mostly comprising three members (94%), with smaller proportions of two-member (4%) and four-member teams (2%). Some teams produced multiple products. A pre-academic year survey showed that 85% of students lacked prior experience with PBL activities, 10% had some experience, and 5% were unfamiliar with the PBL approach.

Table 1. Summary of the enrolment rates, sample size (both with percentage distribution of male -M- and female -F- students), total number of student teams and functional products generated per academic year in the OSOR project.

Academic year	Enrolled	Sample	Number of student teams	Number of functional products
2018-19	70 [83% M, 17% F]	40 (57%) [80% M, 20% F]	23	23
2019-20 (COVID-19 pandemic)	49 [94% M, 6% F]	6 (12%) [83% M, 17% F]	18	2
2020-21	46 [65% M, 35% F]	42 (91%) [71% M, 29% F]	16	23
2021-22	39 [82% M, 12% F]	26 (67%) [85% M, 15% F]	13	18

4.2 Instruments

Ad hoc questionnaires and knowledge tests, designed following literature guidelines and validated statistically (see Section 5.1), were used to address the research questions. Aligned with the ENAEE EUR-ACE accreditation standards¹⁰, the instruments were categorized as follows: (i) to gather opinions about the methodology and subject, (ii) to evaluate technical knowledge and soft skills, and (iii) to assess the products.

Students completed the instruments at the start (pre-) and end (post-) of the semester, both within 15 minutes during the first and last weeks of classes, respectively. The paired instruments (pre, post) contained identical questions and were rated on a Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree), except for the technical knowledge test (scored 0 - 10), and the open comments. Responses were anonymous, but they were later linked via a student-provided identification number (last four digits of their phone number). All instruments were completed online under instructor supervision. Before the intervention, students received written information about the objectives of the project, data confidentiality, and their right to withdraw consent. The written consent from every student was obtained prior to their participation.

4.2.1 Instrument for gathering opinions on the methodology and the subject

The evaluation of the methodology and the course overall was conducted through a semester-end questionnaire administered to all courses. The opinion survey (Table 3) followed the approach of (Rodríguez et al. 2015). Four questions (OSOR-Qi) gathered students' opinion on the OSOR, while another four (MT-Qi) focused on feedback about the MT subject. The final question (MT-Q4) was open-ended, inviting students to provide comments or suggestions for improving both the OSOR project and the MT subject further.

4.2.2 Instruments to assess technical knowledge and soft skill acquisition

The assessment of students' technical knowledge evolved over time. In 2018-19, self-assessment questions were used, but in the rest of the academic years, we transitioned to objective tests comprised of knowledge-based questions (*etka*-test). Since these methods are not directly comparable, *etka*-test data were used to analyse the 2020-21 and 2021-22 periods, while broader cohort comparisons relied on students' academic rates. Soft skill acquisition was consistently measured via self-perception surveys (*SPoSS*-survey) across all years. Both the *etka*-test and *SPoSS*-survey were administered at the start (pre-) and end (post-) of the semesters, with learning gains computed for each student as: $G = (\text{post-score} - \text{pre-score})$. Detailed descriptions of these instruments are provided below.

Essential technical knowledge acquisition (etka) test: The etka-test aligns with the learning areas of EUR-ACE accreditation standards: "Knowledge and Understanding," "Engineering Analysis," and "Engineering Practice" ¹⁰. Briefly, it consists of 40 multiple-choice technical questions covering key concepts and procedures in the MT syllabus. An example questions is: "In electrochemical machining, the workpiece is not thermally affected". This approach provides an objective measure of the acquisition of essential academic knowledge by course completion ³.

Self-perception on soft skills (SPoSS) survey: This survey aligns with the learning areas of the EUR-ACE accreditation standards (ENAE 2023): "Making Judgements", "Communication and Team-working" and "Lifelong Learning". It includes seven questions (SPoSS-Qi), detailed in Table 6, to assess students' self-perception of their personal and interpersonal skills. While self-reported learning gains are useful for evaluating skills, ^{3,18,40}, especially for group comparisons ⁴¹, the reliance on subjective data remains a limitation of our work.

4.2.3 Instrument to assess the OSOR products

Three instructors involved in the project conducted a retrospective evaluation of the products developed during 2018-19, 2020-21 and 2021-22 academic years, using a methodology similar to ²⁰. This assessment focused on four key elements aligned with the OSOR pedagogical model (Fig. 1) as follows:

1. "The problem" assesses the *complexity* of the case and the severity of the *user's disability* in relation to it. This element directly affects students' perceptions of task usefulness, ease of execution, and anticipated success, aligning with the "Presage" factor in the OSOR pedagogical model.
2. "The process" evaluates the *initial idea* proposed to solve de case, the level of team *involvement*, the *teamwork* dynamics, the *number of prototypes* produced, and team's *perseverance*. It also considers the extent of team-patient *interaction*. This element reflects concepts related to the "Process" factor in the OSOR pedagogical model, which pertains to students' active participation, effort and persistence in the face of challenges.
3. "The solution" examines the *effective use of various technologies* and the *appropriateness* of the final products. This element is tied to the "Product" item in the OSOR pedagogical model.
4. "The presentation" focuses on the *quality of documentation*, *video*, and *oral capabilities* during the final public presentation. This element is also related to the item "Product" of the OSOR pedagogical model.

Each element was rated on a three-level scale: Low (0), Medium (1), and High (2).

4.3 Data analysis

Numerical data were analysed using statistical techniques, while descriptive data underwent thematic analysis. Survey consistency and reliability was assessed via Cronbach's alpha, while sampling adequacy using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure. Shapiro-Wilk test evaluated data normality.

Nonparametric tests, including the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test for paired samples (pre- and post-scores), and the Mann-Whitney U-test and Kruskal-Wallis test for the comparison of samples from different academic courses were used for analysing non-normal data. For normally distributed data, the Student's t-test was applied. The significance level of the tests for declaring a probability value as significant was set to 0.050. Descriptive statistics summarized both survey and product evaluation results. Spearman's correlation measured variable relationships, with the correlation coefficient (r) serving as the measure of effect size. In accordance with Cohen's guidelines ⁴², $0.1 \leq r < 0.3$ indicates a small effect size (no statistically significant difference between paired scores), $0.3 \leq r < 0.5$ a medium effect size, and $r \geq 0.5$ a large effect size (significantly different paired scores). Data were processed with Microsoft Excel and analysed using IBM SPSS and Python.

Students' responses to the MT-Q4 open-ended question were thematically analysed to identify patterns and relationships, following the methodology outlined by Braun and Clarke⁴³ by using NVivo 14 software.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Validity, consistency, and reliability of the surveys. Normality tests

The content validity of the ad hoc tests and surveys was confirmed through expert review. Their consistency and reliability were assessed by statistical analyses with Cronbach's α coefficients of 0.86 and 0.75 for the *SPoSS* and *Opinion* surveys, respectively. These values demonstrate the appropriate reliability of both surveys as calculated Cronbach's α -coefficients > 0.70 ⁴⁴. Furthermore, the KMO coefficients for the *SPoSS* and the *Opinion* surveys were 0.70 and 0.84, respectively. As both meet or exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.7⁴⁵, this is an indication of adequate sampling processes.

Regarding the normality of the data, students' final scores in MT followed a normal distribution in all four academic years, which allowed the use of the Student's t-test. On the contrary, pre- and post-survey data, *etka* test results, and product assessments did not exhibit normality.

Overall, this preliminary analysis confirmed the reliability, and appropriate sampling of the surveys and guided in selecting the appropriate statistical method based on data normality.

5.2 How did the project evolve over the four academic years?

The OSOR project has undergone significant evolution over four academic years, with each iteration introducing new features and enhancements to its framework. For clarity, we will use the nomenclature of "versions" instead of "academic years". Table 2 outlines this evolution, highlighting three distinctive features: the origin of the cases to solve, the beneficiaries of the products, and the level of interaction with experts and patients.

Table 2. Main characteristics of the four OSOR versions included in the study.

Version	Project settings	Who proposes the cases? Who benefits from the products?	Interactions between teams and external entities
Version 1 (2018-19)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Duration: Long-term project (14 weeks). Aim: Improving the quality of life for people in a dependency situation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Instructors present the project within an ambiguous and open-ended context. Teams propose hypothetical cases. No specific beneficiary is assigned. 	No interactions (Not programmed)
Version 2 (2019-20)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design criteria: Teams should design the products from scratch. All designs are uploaded to the internet. Manufacturing criteria: Any manufacturing technology available at the university makerspace or the MT workshop. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two external institutions propose 11 cases from 6 patients. Every product has a specific beneficiary. Needs are well defined but solutions are open-ended. 	No interactions (Due to COVID-19 restrictions)
Version 3 (2020-21)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Budget: Limited (although flexible). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Three institutions proposed 19 cases from 9 patients. The remaining specifications are the same as Variant 2. 	Some interactions with experts (Due to remaining COVID-19 restrictions)

Version 4 (2021-22)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Four institutions proposed 30 cases from 16 patients. • The remaining specifications are the same as Variant 2. 	Some interactions with expert and patients
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The progression of the project reflects its adaptation to external challenges, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, and the emphasis on establishing collaboration with external institutions. In Version 1, the absence of such partnerships led instructors to allow students to propose their own hypothetical cases, define solutions, and select suitable manufacturing technologies from those available, creating, in this way, a broad, open-ended framework. For example, Fig. 3a shows a hair dryer support for individuals with limited upper limb mobility. This product was not created for a specific beneficiary but rather as a general solution. The design incorporates three technologies (3D printing, welding, and metal forming) and is equipped with a DC motor and controlled by two switches.

Fig. 3. Some representative examples of the delivered products in different versions. Version 1: A support for the automated motion of a hair dryer for individuals with limited upper limb mobility (a). Version 2: A prosthesis for a woman who lost two fingers (b). Version 3: A finger exercise product for a patient with stroke sequelae (c). Version 4: An adapted arm support for a person with multiple sclerosis to prevent the arm from falling off the wheelchair armrest (d).

The OSOR Version 2 introduced partnerships with two external institutions, enabling experts to propose patient needs while leaving solutions open-ended. This approach ensured products were tailored to specific users that were selected at the beginning of the semester. However, the mandatory confinement due to the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted the main activities programmed: prototyping, teamwork, and interactions with users and experts. No contingency plan was in place for dealing with this situation⁴⁶ and therefore, many promising ideas remained unfeasible by the end of the semester, such as the complex prosthesis for a woman missing two fingers shown in Fig. 3b.

Version 3 was implemented during the ongoing pandemic but under less restrictive conditions. Similar to Version 2, patient-proposed cases formed the foundation of the projects. In this version, a third external institution joined the OSOR initiative, contributing numerous interesting cases. Although direct engagement with patients was still not permitted, some teams were able to interact with experts. A representative example of Version 3 (Fig. 3c) is a finger exerciser designed for a 56-year-old male chronic post-stroke patient. The device, made with 3D printed ergonomic parts, was developed under direct the supervision of a physician from one of the collaborating institutions.

Lastly, OSOR Version 4 followed a similar structure to previous academic years but was conducted in a normal environment, free from pandemic restrictions. The inclusion of a fourth institution, increased the number of cases available. Unlike previous versions, students were encouraged to meet the patients to test their prototypes and receive direct feedback to improve their usability. However, few teams decided to follow this approach likely due to the additional time required to accomplish these tasks and the lack of grading incentives, as it was not assessed and did not impact their final grades. One team, however, tested at least four prototypes with their assigned patient, which even lead to empathetic bond, creating an active collaboration that notably enhanced the delivered product. Fig. 3d depicts the patient from this case, a 48-year-old man with multiple sclerosis, using a 3D-printed ergonomic support, demonstrating that the design prevented his arm from falling off the wheelchair.

Overall, the evolution of the OSOR project highlights three key aspects: (i) The origin of proposed cases with an increase emphasis on producing patient-centred designs; (ii) The expansion of the collaboration with external institutions through a close and dynamic interaction with experts and patients; and (iii) The improved in the quality of the products by a more refine iterative prototyping, and despite challenges posed by the pandemic and varying levels of student engagement. These advancements facilitated the transition of OSOR from PBL (Version 1), where students developed their own hypothetical cases, to CBL with elements of SL (Versions 3 and 4), where students addressed real-world patient cases provided by local institutions.

5.3 What were the implications of altering the responsibility for proposing the cases?

Student feedback across all versions reveals how the evolution of the OSOR project shaped their perceptions of both the project and the course, particularly highlighting the impact of the transition from working on hypothetical cases proposed by the students themselves to addressing real cases provided by patients from external institutions. These insights are summarized in the *Opinion Survey* (Table 3), focusing on the learning process, workload, and overall experience.

Table 3. Questions and results (scale from 1 to 4) of the Opinion survey. Items with statistically significant differences (p -value < 0.05) between versions are marked with asterisks (*).

Question	Version 1 (2018-19)		Version 3 (2020-21)		Version 4 (2021-22)	
	AVG	SD	AVG	SD	AVG	SD
OSOR-Qi						
1. I believe that with OSOR project, concepts are better learned compared to the traditional teaching model.	3.6	0.6	3.8	0.4	3.5	0.8
2. I believe that the OSOR project develops personal skills that are not acquired with the traditional teaching model.	3.8	0.3	3.9	0.2	3.8	0.3
3. I believe that the OSOR project involves more work than the traditional teaching model. *	3.3*	0.6	3.8*	0.4	3.5	0.7
4. I am satisfied with the workload that the OSOR project entails in comparison to the results obtained	3.8	0.3	3.6	0.5	3.5	0.4
MT-Qi						
1. Overall, what level of interest did you have in the MT subject?	3.7	0.4	3.7	0.4	3.6	0.5
2. Overall, how important do you consider the subject for your education as an engineer?	3.7	0.5	3.8	0.4	3.7	0.4
3. Overall, how challenging do you find the subject? *	2.2*	0.4	2.5*	0.6	2.4	0.7

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4. Provide any comments or suggestions for improving the subject	(No numerical value)
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Across all the OSOR versions, students expressed highly positive perceptions of both the project (Fig. 4a) and the MT subject (Fig. 4b).

Students in Version 3 rated the workload during OSOR as significantly higher (OSOR-Q3, $p = 0.004$, Kruskal-Wallis test) and the subject as more challenging (MT-Q3, $p = 0.046$, Kruskal-Wallis test) compared to their peers in Version 1. This difference reflects the shift in project complexity: while students in Version 1 worked on hypothetical cases they created themselves, those in Version 3 designed products for an assigned real patient, adding layers of difficulty and realism to the tasks. These findings are consistent with observations by ³, who noted that students tackling complex, open-ended challenges often perceive assignments as more difficult due to their limited prior experience with such tasks. Although all OSOR versions maintained an open-ended framework, the autonomy in generating their own cases in Version 1 allowed students to minimize ambiguity and tailor projects to their existing knowledge, thereby making the tasks more manageable. In contrast, addressing real patient cases in Version 3 introduced higher levels of uncertainty, a factor identified by ⁴⁷ as significantly influencing students' experiences with CBL.

Fig. 4. Students' perception of the OSOR project (a) and MT subject (b). Mean subject's final scores per academic year (c), and by gender (d). Semantic network that defines the influence of the OSOR project in the Manufacturing Technology subject (e). Vertical black bars represent 95% confidence interval of the mean value (bootstrap)

This underscores the importance of structured teaching frameworks and immediate feedback to help students navigate complex, open-ended tasks effectively. These components were integral to the OSOR project's design, ensuring students received the guidance needed to succeed in tackling real-world problems. By balancing complexity with appropriate support, the project fostered high levels of satisfaction with the learning experience, despite the increased challenges presented in Version 3.

For a deeper analysis of student perceptions, responses to MT-Q4 (*“Provide some comments or suggestions for improving the subject”*) were examined for major themes, key points, and patterns. A total of 84 comments were collected, distributed as follows: 10 from Version 1 (14% participation), 42 from Version 3 (50%), and 32 from Version 4 (38%). Three main themes emerged: (i) satisfaction with the subject, (ii) satisfaction with the OSOR, and (iii) suggestions. The frequency of these themes per academic year is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Themes, codes, and frequencies obtained from the qualitative analysis of students' comments. The parentheses show the proportions.

Theme	Code	Frequency			
		Total	2018-19 (Version 1)	2020-21 (Version 3)	2021-22 (Version 4)
Satisfaction with the subject	Practical-MT	21	2 (13%)	13 (21%)	6 (12%)
	Everything is OK	22	1 (6%)	8 (13%)	13 (26%)
	Well organized-MT	17	5 (31%)	8 (13%)	4 (8%)
	Motivating-MT	16	0 (0%)	10 (16%)	6 (12%)
	Learning-MT	16	1 (6%)	9 (14%)	6 (12%)
	Useful-MT	8	0 (0%)	4 (6%)	4 (8%)
Satisfaction with the OSOR	Practical-OSOR	9	2 (13%)	1 (2%)	6 (12%)
	Motivating-OSOR	7	4 (25%)	2 (3%)	1 (2%)
Suggestions	Practical	13	1 (6%)	8 (13%)	4 (8%)

The most repeated code within these three themes was the one referring to the **practical aspect** of the knowledge imparted, as reflected in comments such as, *“The OSOR project seems to me a very original idea to apply the acquired knowledge”* (Version 1), *“I think this subject is very important, because it brings us a little closer to the practical part of engineering, and not to be all the time with theory”* (Version 3), and *“I believe in its usefulness (OSOR) to make us put into practice more important skills such as conflict resolution, negotiating, communicating properly, initiative, etc.”* (Version 4). Engineering students often seek hands-on learning, and an overemphasis on theoretical, lecture-heavy classes may lead to significant frustration²⁶. Students in Version 3 followed by those in Version 4, felt attracted to real problems, and emphasized the importance of putting knowledge into practice compared to their peers in Version 1.

Students frequently praised the smooth organization of the course with an increasing number of comments each year, such as **“Everything is OK”** and **“It is well organized”**. Representative feedback includes: *“Both the approach and the development of the subject could be described as excellent”* (Version 1), *“I think that the functioning and organization of the subject are fine”* (Version 3), *“It seems to me that everything is well organized and with regular follow-ups to not leave stuff for the end of the semester”* (Version 4). Students in Versions 3 and 4, which involved assigned patients, particularly appreciated the well-structured teaching framework and the effective management of the project. **Motivation** merged as a recurring theme, with Version 3 students, followed by Version 4, expressing the highest levels of enthusiasm for the subject. Illustrative comments include: *“The subject, as it has been taught, is very dynamic, ... and as a way of teaching, more interest is put than in the rest of the subjects taught in a traditional way”* (Version 3), and *“The subject is great as it is, it is very enjoyable”* (Version 4). Students also highlighted the motivational impact of the OSOR project, stating: *“I think that this project (OSOR) helps and motivates us, since it is very practical and not so theoretical”* (Version 1), *“thanks to the OSOR project you have an extra motivation to help someone”* (Version 3). Overall, the various factors introduced across the different versions significantly enhanced students' motivation and engagement with the subject, especially in Versions 3 and 4.

Regarding their **learning process**, students in Versions 3 and 4 emphasized this aspect more frequently than those in Version 1 with comments such as “*It seems to me that learning things by doing them is the best way to internalize the concepts and stuff learned in class*” (Version 3), or “*I believe the applied model helps students learn more*” (Version 4). These differences are understandable because Versions 3 and 4 involved creating products for real patients with immediate needs. Moreover, students in Version 3 and 4 (unlike those in Version 1) frequently commented on the “**usefulness of what they learned**” connecting it directly to their professional futures. For example, a student from Version 3 stated, “*In my opinion it is a very useful subject for our professional future*”, and another from Version 4 added, “*I think that this learning model makes the student understand what is really useful for a future in the working world, as opposed to what is applied in subjects with a traditional teaching method*”.

The stronger focus on the relevance and utility of their learning in Versions 3 and 4 aligns with ⁴⁸, who found that recognizing the relevance of their studies significantly increases students’ engagement and sense of purpose in CBL.

The semantic network summarizing the thematic analysis of students’ comments is illustrated in Fig. 4e. It revealed that a well-structured, practically oriented project with a social purpose, as embodied in the OSOR pedagogical model (Fig. 1), positively influenced students’ perception of the usefulness of the involved tasks for their future engineering careers. This approach seemed to enhance their well-being, motivation, and engagement, fostering persistence and participation despite challenges. As noted by ²⁶ tackling real, practical challenges with tangible outcomes significantly boosts motivation and engagement. This was particularly visible in Versions 3 and 4 that involved collaboration with local entities and their patients.

To directly address the research question regarding the implications of altering the responsibility for proposing the cases, the transition from hypothetical cases (aligned with a PBL approach) to real patient-centred projects (aligned with a CBL approach) profoundly impacted students’ perceptions of both the OSOR and the subject. While this shift from PBL to CBL made the project and course more demanding, students consistently appreciated the practical nature of the assignments, recognizing their real-world relevance and impact, which significantly boosted their satisfaction and motivation to learn.

5.4 How did the educational framework contribute to enhancing students’ learning?

To address this question, we examined student learning from three perspectives detailed in the following subsections.

5.4.1 Acquisition of Technical Knowledge

The acquisition of technical knowledge by the students was assessed using the *etka* test in Versions 3 and 4 (Table 5) and final MT subject scores in Versions 1, 3, and 4 (Fig. 4c and d). The *etka* test was introduced in Version 3, so Version 1 was not evaluated with this method.

Table 5. Results of the *etka* test on students’ technical knowledge acquisition in Versions 3 and 4, visualized in a scale from 0 to 10. Data from different academic years were compared using a Mann-Whitney U test (M-W).

		Pre- <i>etka</i> (from 0 to 10)				M-W	Post- <i>etka</i> (from 0 to 10)			M-W	Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks between pre- and post-			Learning gain (from 0 to 10)			M-W
	N	M	MED	SD	p- value	M	MED	SD	p- value	p- value	Effect size (r)	M	MED	SD	p- value		

Version 3 (2020-21)	42	2.27	1.19	1.63	0.43	8.19	8.55	1.47	0.86	<0.001	0.9	5.92	5.60	1.77	0.46
Version 4 (2021-22)	26	2.97	2.73	1.64		8.17	8.24	1.28		<0.001	0.9	5.52	5.27	1.86	

Table 5 indicates that initial technical knowledge among students in Versions 3 and 4 was comparable, as *pre-*etka** scores revealed no significant differences (p -value = 0.43, Mann-Whitney U test). However, both versions demonstrated significant learning gains, with substantial improvements between pre- and post-scores ($p < 0.001$, Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test; effect size = 0.9). Specifically, Version 3 exhibited a 261% improvement, while Version 4 showed a 186% increase, with no significant differences between the two versions ($p = 0.46$, Mann-Whitney U test).

These findings align with those of³ who reported that CBL effectively fosters technical knowledge acquisition among engineering students. They emphasize that working on open-ended, complex problems, such as those faced in the OSOR project, requires knowledge integration and practical application, which are essential for achieving more effective technical learning outcomes.

To compare the three versions, the final scores shown in Fig. 4c indicate that scores remained consistently high across all academic years. However, students in Versions 3 and 4, who were exposed to real patient scenarios, achieved significantly higher grades than those in Version 1, which was developed without patient involvement ($p < 0.001$, one-way ANOVA). The awareness of the direct impact of their solutions on patients likely motivated students to master technical concepts and apply them effectively. This motivation, as highlighted by⁴⁸, may therefore play a critical role in enhancing academic performance. Similarly, previous study⁴⁹ observed improved academic performance (and well-being) in a second-year mechanical engineering course applying elements of CBL. They concluded that the fundamental knowledge gained on the first courses of engineering degrees might be more effectively acquired through projects that integrate only some specific elements of the CBL within a specific subject area. This underscores the versatility of CBL to be adapted to the needs of any given subject, and the work done with the MT subject is a good example of that.

Another factor influencing knowledge acquisition in OSOR may be students' exposure to unfamiliar problems. A previous study⁵⁰ argue that engaging in out-of-the-ordinary challenges, such as assisting individuals in dependency, fosters deeper learning than addressing conventional and expected engineering problems. These types of experiences not only enrich the engineering profession and its societal appreciation but also promote a deeper understanding of solutions based on engineering in a more social context.

However, other authors mention that CBL may hinder "deep" technical knowledge acquisition due to the time required for interactions with social stakeholders or the target audience of the product designed⁴⁷. This may not be captured in our study because interaction of the teams with the patients have not been as consistent as planned. In the future, interactions will be promoted to identify potential negative impacts.

On the other hand, gender (Fig. 4d) did not show impact in the final scores across the academic years (p -value = 0.96, two-way ANOVA test). However, since the introduction of patients in Versions 3 and 4, there appears to be a trend where female students outperform males in average final grades, reversing the pattern observed in previous years. Some authors⁵¹, suggest that females are generally more motivated toward service and helping throughout their careers than males. Nevertheless, this difference may not stem from an inherent predisposition of females, but rather from historical educational practices that have traditionally encouraged these behaviours in women. In this regard, the OSOR project offers a valuable opportunity to balance these differences by providing all students with equal chances to develop their social responsibility and service-oriented skills. Future studies will further investigate this trend to determine its persistence and potential underlying factors.

5.4.2 Development of personal and interpersonal skills

This section examines the influence of the different OSOR versions on students' self-perception of their acquisition of personal and interpersonal skills, as measured by the *SPoSS* survey. The results are detailed in Table 6 and Fig. 5.

Table 6. Questions and results (mean score) of the SPoSS survey (scale from 1 to 4). Statistically significant differences (p -value <0.05) between pre- and post-scores are marked with asterisks. "G" is the mean score of the perceived soft skill gain.

SPoSS-Qi	Version 1 (2018-19)			Version 3 (2020-21)			Version 4 (2021-22)		
	Pre	Post	G	Pre	Post	G	Pre	Post	G
1. I consider myself a person with good oral communication skills	2.6	3.1	0.5*	2.6	3.1	0.5*	2.8	3.2	0.5*
2. I consider myself a person with the ability to work in a team	3.3	3.5	0.3*	3.1	3.3	0.3	3.3	3.4	0.1
3. I consider myself a person with skills for leading teams	2.9	3.5	0.5*	2.7	3.2	0.5*	2.9	3.4	0.5*
4. I consider myself a creative person when it comes to problem-solving	3.0	3.5	0.5*	2.9	3.1	0.2	3.0	3.2	0.2
5. I consider myself a person with the ability to extract the truly important aspects from texts and everyday situations	2.9	3.2	0.4*	2.7	3.2	0.5*	2.9	3.2	0.3*
6. I consider myself a person with the ability to manage my time efficiently and self-regulate in my tasks	2.5	2.9	0.4*	2.4	2.6	0.2	2.7	2.7	0.0
7. I consider myself a proactive person , always proposing and implementing solutions, and less reactive (feeling more comfortable receiving instructions)	2.8	3.2	0.4*	2.7	3.0	0.3*	2.9	3.1	0.3*

Initially, students' perceptions were very similar across academic years, with no statistically significant differences observed in pre-SPoSS scores (p -value = 0.13, Kruskal-Wallis test). However, a moderate increase in perceived soft skills was reported after each academic year. This moderate increase appears to be common among engineering students without prior experience in PBL or CBL activities, such as in this case, as they tend to overestimate their skills before starting such projects but provide more realistic self-assessments upon completion^{18,26,52,53}.

Interestingly, students in Version 1 were the only group to show statistically significant gains across all soft skills (p -value < 0.05 , Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test, with large effect sizes, $r \geq 0.5$), achieving peak values in most areas. Working on their own cases, without a target patient, might have fostered a stronger sense of ownership and control, positively impacting the development of their soft skill, which was also reported by several authors^{12,49}. However, this autonomy may have created a false sense of accomplishment, as the students' products were not finally tested with real patients. In contrast, students in Versions 3 and 4, while not having significant direct interaction with their assigned patients, gained a closer approximation to the reality of the problem through videos and photos illustrating the motor limitations of their patients. This exposure may have heightened their awareness that their products, while potentially helpful, might not be entirely suitable in some aspects. This real-world context likely contributed to a different perception of their soft skills, fostering a more critical evaluation of their abilities. Further analysis is needed to draw more definitive conclusions.

Statistically significant gains ($p < 0.05$, Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test) were observed across all courses in four key areas: oral communication, leadership, capacity for synthesis, and proactivity.

Among these, oral communication showed the highest gains across all OSOR versions, largely due to the emphasis on oral presentations as a core component of the project (Fig. 2). This finding aligns with the literature, where oral communication is frequently identified as the skill most improved through PBL and CBL methodologies¹⁸.

Leadership, though less cited in the literature^{3,5,18}, was consistently perceived by students as one of the most enhanced skills across OSOR versions. Similarly, capacity for synthesis and proactivity, closely related to

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3 "reasoning for complexity" ⁵⁴, seemed to improve through students' exposure to open-ended, ill-defined
4 projects, further highlighting the value of the OSOR framework in fostering these competencies.
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6 Teamwork, widely recognized in the literature as a key skill often improved through PBL and CBL¹⁸, did not
7 show significant improvement in our study, except for a minimal gain in Version 1. This aligns with findings
8 by ⁵⁵, who also reported no significant gains in teamwork. Notably, teamwork repeatedly received the highest
9 initial and final evaluations, suggesting an overestimation of this skill at the start of the course, which may
10 have contributed to the low recorded gains by the end of the course.
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13 Efficient time management consistently received the lowest initial and final ratings across all years, with
14 minimal gains, particularly in Versions 3 and 4. Similar results regarding time management in PBL were
15 observed by ^{56 18,53}, with others also highlighting struggles with time constraints in CBL (Doulougeri et al.
16 2024). This issue likely made the OSOR project more demanding for students in Versions 3 and 4. According
17 to ¹⁴, students in CBL must not only master their subject knowledge and prepare for exams but also tackle
18 real-world challenges and effectively communicate their solutions to clients or external stakeholders. While
19 progress in time management was limited, some authors ⁵⁷ suggest that PBL and CBL can improve this skill
20 through shared responsibility among team members, highlighting the potential for further improvement in
21 OSOR.
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Fig. 5. Pre- and post-SPoSS mean values of each of the items assessed in the SPoSS-survey (Table 6). Vertical black bars represent 95% confidence interval of the mean value (bootstrap).

5.4.3 Development and efficacy of the provided solutions

The 64 products from OSOR Versions 1, 3, and 4 were evaluated together, with the results detailed in Table 7.

The element “The problem” varied significantly across versions (p -value < 0.05 , Kruskal-Wallis H test) driven by the inclusion of real patients in Versions 3 and 4. This resulted in medium-high scores in the sub-element of *user's disability*. Overall, case *complexity* was consistently rated medium-high across all versions.

Table 7. List of elements and sub-elements used to evaluate products. The reported metrics include mean score (M), median score (MED) and standard deviation (SD). The sub-elements that showed statistically significant differences (p -value < 0.05) between OSOR versions are marked with an asterisk. The sub-elements were assessed on a three-level scale: low (0), medium (1), and high (2).

Element	Sub-elements	Version 1			Version 3			Version 4		
		M	MED	SD	M	MED	SD	M	MED	SD
The problem*	Problem complexity	1.4	2.0	0.7	1.5	1.5	0.5	1.5	2.0	0.7
	User's disability *	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	1.0	0.3	1.5	2.0	0.5
	<i>Total</i>	0.7	1.0	0.4	1.3	1.3	0.3	1.5	1.5	0.4
The process*	Initial idea	1.0	1.0	0.8	1.4	1.0	0.5	0.8	1.0	0.9
	Teamwork	1.5	2.0	0.7	1.8	2.0	0.6	1.3	1.0	0.8
	Involvement	1.4	2.0	0.7	1.7	2.0	0.6	1.4	2.0	0.9
	Number of prototypes	1.5	2.0	0.5	1.8	2.0	0.4	1.6	2.0	0.5
	Perseverance	1.6	2.0	0.7	1.6	2.0	0.8	1.2	2.0	0.9
	Interaction with patient/expert*	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.5	0.6	1.0	0.7
	<i>Total</i>	1.2	1.3	0.5	1.4	1.5	0.4	1.2	1.5	0.6
The solution	Effective use of technologies	1.2	1.0	0.7	1.4	1.0	0.5	1.2	1.0	0.8
	Solution appropriateness	1.2	1.0	0.6	1.5	2.0	0.6	1.2	1.0	0.6
	<i>Total</i>	1.2	1.0	0.6	1.5	1.5	0.5	1.2	1.0	0.7
The presentation	Documentation quality*	1.3	1.0	0.7	1.8	2.0	0.4	0.9	1.0	0.8
	Video quality	1.0	1.0	0.8	1.1	1.0	0.9	1.3	1.0	0.6
	Oral capabilities	1.3	2.0	0.8	1.4	1.0	0.6	1.2	1.0	0.6
	<i>Total</i>	1.2	1.3	0.6	1.4	1.5	0.4	1.2	1.3	0.5
TOTAL		1.1	1.3	0.6	1.7	1.4	0.6	1.2	1.4	0.7

The product development process, or “The process”, also revealed statistically significant differences between versions (p -value < 0.05 , Kruskal-Wallis H test), with Version 3 outperforming Version 1. Teams generally achieved medium-high scores in *teamwork*, *involvement*, and *perseverance*, despite some unsuccessful *initial ideas*, such as the case of Version 4 (with low-medium scores). Students produced an adequate *number of prototypes* (scoring between 1 and 2), though patient interaction remained limited (ratings between 0 and 1) but increased over time showing significant differences between versions (p -value < 0.05 , Kruskal-Wallis H test).

Also, “The solution” and “The presentation” elements showed no significant differences across versions. Overall, these findings show that the production process employed different suitable technologies (“*Effective use of technologies*”), and the final products usually handled the problem for which they were designed (“*solution appropriateness*”), leading to medium-high ratings for “The solution” element. The *Documentation quality*, a sub-element of “The presentation,” varied significantly ($p < 0.05$, Kruskal-Wallis H test), with Version 3 producing the most well written reports. In summary, product presentations were well-developed across all versions, achieving medium-high ratings.

In summary, students in Versions 3 and 4 (aligned with a CBL approach), could initially have perceived lower ease of execution and anticipated less success compared to those in Version 1 (aligned with a PBL approach), primarily due to the greater complexity of addressing real patient needs. However, they ultimately developed solutions more efficiently and delivered higher-quality products. This outcome was likely driven by the motivation derived from knowing their work would directly benefit specific individuals with urgent needs.

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4 This finding suggests that the increased task complexity was outweighed by the perceived usefulness and
5 impact of the project. Furthermore, a well-structured project design, combined with the assurance of
6 immediate feedback at each stage and social support from family and friends, likely contributed to this success.
7 Such support may have fostered active participation and perseverance, enabling students to overcome
8 challenges, as outlined in the OSOR pedagogical model (Fig. 1). Several authors have similarly noted
9 increased student engagement and motivation in CBL projects, particularly when they address real-world
10 issues with a tangible, positive impact on people's lives ³.

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13 This article demonstrates the success of the OSOR project deliverables, with all student teams successfully
14 creating functional solutions for their assigned cases, addressing a key but often underreported aspect of CBL.
15 As noted by ²⁷, most CBL studies focus on student experience and skill acquisition while frequently
16 overlooking objective success criteria for the challenges themselves. By evaluating the outcomes of OSOR,
17 this study seeks to bridge this gap in the CBL literature.

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20 To directly address the research question regarding how the OSOR educational framework contributed to
21 enhancing students' learning, we can state that engaging with open-ended, unfamiliar and complex challenges,
22 as seen in the CBL version of OSOR (Versions 3 and 4), fosters deep technical learning. Despite the increased
23 complexity of addressing real patient needs, students delivered high-quality solutions, likely motivated by the
24 impact their work could have on specific individuals. The framework also supported the development of soft
25 skills, particularly in oral communication, leadership, capacity for synthesis, and proactivity. In summary, the
26 OSOR project's educational framework highlights the potential of socially oriented CBL initiatives to prepare
27 students for the dynamic and evolving demands of modern engineering practice.

30 6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

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33 This study has several limitations and future studies are needed. (1) We have not included control groups for
34 comparison across the academic years. This is a common issue in AL-based approaches ³. Allowing students
35 to opt out of OSOR evaluation process could address this, for instance. However, we can anticipate that most
36 of them would likely choose participating in the project, making the recruitment of a control group unfeasible.
37 (2) We have relied our initial assessment on students' self-evaluation of their learning progress. While later
38 courses included a technical knowledge test (the *etka* test), soft skills were still measured through self-
39 perception, which may be biased or inaccurate. Future evaluations could use validated benchmarks and
40 surveys completed by both students and instructors, as suggested by previous studies ¹⁸ and ⁵⁸. (3) The low
41 number of female students per course limited the gender-based analysis. This limitation is reflecting a broader
42 issue in the engineering field ⁵⁹. Future research could include focus groups methodologies to better explore
43 gender-related mechanisms ^{60,61}. Note that the study relied on a binary gender framework. A more inclusive
44 approach, incorporating diverse demographic factors, will be considered in future iterations to examine their
45 effects on learning, motivation, and satisfaction. (4) This study was conducted on a small sample of
46 engineering students from a single university. Therefore, its results cannot be generalized to populations
47 outside this group. Future research should engage a more diverse range of institutions.

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51 Future editions of the OSOR project could encourage students to engage more directly with stakeholders,
52 which includes patients and experts from local institutions as well as professionals from industry. Through
53 this process, students might gain additional valuable real-world experience. Patients feedback on product
54 usability will also be incorporated using tools like the Systems Usability Scale ⁶². Additionally, future research
55 will focus on assessing students' development of the skill "Social Responsibility", for which targeted surveys
56 such as those recommended by ⁶³⁻⁶⁵ might be adequate.

59 7. CONCLUSION

This paper explores the impact of the OSOR project on the learning outcomes and perceptions of industrial engineering undergraduates. Launched in 2018 within the Manufacturing Technology (MT) course at a public university in northern Spain, the OSOR addresses the lack of assistive products for people in a situation of dependency. The experiences of 108 students over three years were analysed, combining tests, surveys, academic results, and a retrospective evaluation of a total of 64 products delivered, to gain insights into the evolution and effectiveness of this educational framework.

The OSOR project transitioned from a PBL approach (Version 1), where students proposed their own hypothetical cases, to a CBL framework with elements of SL (Versions 3 and 4), where students addressed real-world patient cases provided by local institutions. Each version significantly improved technical knowledge acquisition and moderately influenced soft skill development in students. Only students in Version 1 (PBL framework) demonstrated statistically significant gains in self-assessed soft skills, likely due to a higher perception of control over their learning process, although this requires further studies. **These students also perceived a lower workload and found the course less challenging compared to later versions.**

In contrast, students in CBL framework (Versions 3 and 4), who addressed real patient needs, perceived the subject as more demanding but seemed to be more motivated, achieved higher grades, delivered superior products, and provided more positive feedback than the students from previous years (Version 1). Despite the extra effort made by the students, and based on our thematic analyses of their comments, they experienced first-hand the practical utility of the OSOR initiative, fostering motivation and engagement to create optimized solutions. The organizational structure of OSOR also played a crucial role in student satisfaction. A well-designed framework ensured favourable perceptions of the learning objectives among students, provided a supportive learning environment, and promoted their personal well-being.

This study highlights how CBL approaches, such as the OSOR project, can effectively connect real-world challenges with social purpose to enhance student motivation and engagement. In doing so, these initiatives help cultivate the sociotechnical skills, critical for success in modern engineering careers.

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STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

Ethical considerations and consent to participate

This work was carried out with ethics approval from the first author's university Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC), under project 2020/576. All participants provided written informed consent prior to participating.

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Declaration of conflicting interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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Data availability

The research data associated with this article is available at:
<https://investigacion.unirioja.es/datos/67cec15d1f82182aff0d985c>

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